

TRAVEL PACKAGES SUPPORTING SYSTEM

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Abstract. The Travel Packages Supporting System is a comprehensive digital platform designed to streamline the organization, management, and delivery of travel services. This system allows travel agencies to create, manage, and market a wide range of travel packages tailored to various customer preferences and budgets. It integrates features such as inventory management, booking management, and customer relationship management (CRM) to ensure seamless operations. The system also offers an intuitive user interface that enables customers to browse, compare, and book travel packages with ease. Additionally, it includes a powerful analytics tool for agencies to monitor sales performance, customer satisfaction, and market trends. By automating routine tasks and providing real-time data insights, the Travel Packages Supporting System enhances operational efficiency, improves customer experience, and drives business growth in the competitive travel industry.

Keywords: HTML, CSS, Bootstrap5, JavaScript, PHP (Laravel), MySQL

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the improvement in technology has brought the world closer together and empowered individuals with greater knowledge. As a result, there is a growing preference for convenient and efficient ways of doing things, prompting a shift from traditional methods to technological solutions. People now rely on software for storing and accessing information, replacing the need for handwritten records. Likewise, businesses, institutions, and various services such as shops, libraries, and companies utilize management software, websites, and database servers. These tools offer benefits like seamless online and offline services, enhanced security, easy-to-use interfaces, cost-effectiveness, and reduced congestion and waiting times. In my project, I want to develop a travel packages supporting system as this is a specialized software solution designed to automate and streamline the processes involved in managing travel packages. this system serves as a critical tool for travel agencies and companies offering tourism services. It enables them to handle various aspects of travel planning, including package creation, booking, customer management, and payment processing, all within a single, integrated platform.

PROBLEM

This system is designed to implement a maintenance system Travel Packages Supporting System. It uses the main language such as the Front end: HTML, CSS, JavaScript, Bootstrap5, and Back end: PHP Laravel Framework and MySQL Server. HTML ensures

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compatibility and accessibility across browsers and devices, and integrates with CSS and JavaScript to enable dynamic and visually appealing web pages. Laravel- framework provides an alternative to the Web Forms pattern for creating MVC -based web applications. A Database Management System (DBMS) is a defined software system that allows users to define, create, maintain, and control access to the database. A Travel Packages Supporting System offers several advantages for both travel agencies and customers. Automating booking, payment, and itinerary management reduces the time and effort required to manage travel packages. All travel packages, bookings, and customer details are stored in a centralized system, allowing for easy access and management. Customers can view real-time availability of packages, accommodations, and other services, making it easier to plan their trips. By automating manual processes, travel agencies can reduce labour costs and minimize errors, leading to cost savings. As the agency grows, the system can easily accommodate an increasing number of packages, customers, and transactions without significant additional resources. Agencies can easily create, manage, and track promotions and discounts, making it easier to attract and retain customers.

APPROACH

The customer begins with the view home, with navigational options to explore the website further, including the view about and view package, view destination and view contact us. If the customer is interested in a package, they proceed to the booking step, initiating the process of reserving a package. At this point, a critical decision is made at the check email and password, where the system verifies the customer's login credentials. If the credentials are successful login, the flow moves forward to booking confirm and they can view booking. The admin with a login procedure, where the system checks the admin's email and password. If the credentials are correct, the admin is granted access to the system's dashboard. The admin has options: view the dashboard and manage account, category, package, city and booking.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram

The ER diagram provided represents the database structure of a Travel Packages Supporting System, detailing the various entities, their attributes, and relationships. At the center of the schema are the core tables, such as Customer, Package, Booking, Payment, Categories, Cities, and Category package. Each table has a primary key, typically labeled as id, which uniquely identifies each record in the table. For example, the User tables hold information about the users of the system, respectively, with fields for storing their personal details like name, email, phone number, password, and other relevant attributes.

The Package table is central to this system, capturing details about various travel packages offered, such as title, price, duration, and a summary. It is connected to other tables like Booking, which records user bookings by linking to specific users and packages, and Payment, which stores payment details associated with these bookings. The Categories and Cities tables classify the packages by categories and destinations, respectively, with a many-to-many relationship between Categories and Packages managed through the Category_package junction table. This schema allows for a flexible and organized system where packages can be categorized, linked to specific cities, and managed by administrators, all while tracking user interactions through bookings and payments.

Figure 2: Database Design

RESULTS

After the system developed, a travel packages Supporting system involves checking all the features to make sure they work correctly. If bugs or errors are detected during the system testing, the developer may need to correct and fix the bugs immediately. Testing is the process of evaluating a software or system to detect differences between given input and expected output. Testing is conducted to assess the quality of a system hence can be said to be a validation and verification process. System testing is not a testing that is limited only to the development team but it also requires the help from specific outsider to test on the system acceptance. For customer, booking testing includes the login function, and the ability to book

packages and view booking. For admin, authentication testing and the ability to manage account, category, package, city and booking.

Figure 3: Implementation of the System

CONCLUSION

Our Travel Packages Supporting System is an essential tool for modernizing and optimizing the operations of travel agencies. By automating key processes such as booking management, package creation, and customer account handling, the system significantly reduces manual effort and minimizes errors. Secure login procedures and administrative controls ensure that sensitive information is protected, maintaining the integrity of the system. Ultimately, the Travel Package Supporting System is a powerful solution that help travel agencies deliver exceptional service, stays competitive, and grows in an increasingly digital marketplace.

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